

Total RNA isolation from dry and germinating rice seeds for gene expression studies

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Dry seeds normally contain high levels of lipids, storage proteins, polysaccharides, and polyphenols, which decrease RNA yield and quality, factors that are highly important for gene expression analyses (Tai et al 2004). Commercially available RNA isolation kits, which contain guanidium salt solutions, were found to be ineffective in yielding high-quality RNA from dry rice seeds (Fig. 1a) as high levels of polysaccharides prevent the solubilization of RNA after alcohol precipitation (Groppe and Morse 1993). Several other RNA isolation techniques—e.g., SDS-LiCl extraction buffer, SDS-TRIzol method, and high NaCl-LiCl precipitation methods—were also tested but not one was found effective. The method described here is a modification of the procedure described by Stirn et al (1995), which proved to be more effective in yielding high-quality total RNA.

Dry and germinated rice seeds were treated with 10% sodium hypochlorite solution for 10 min, washed three times with sterile distilled water, and dissected in halves to remove most of the starchy endosperm. Around 18 to 20 half-seeds (100 mg) were freeze-dried in liquid nitrogen and ground into powder. Standard precautions for RNA preparation, including the use of DEPC-treated water, were followed. The autoclaved extraction buffer consisted of 1% sarcosyl, 100 mM Tris-HCl, 280 mM NaCl, and 10 mM EDTA at pH 8.5.

The new procedure involved the following steps: (1) an equal volume of extraction buffer was added to the ground tissue together with 10 μ L β -mercaptoethanol per mL of extraction buffer to inhibit RNase activity; (2) phenol (1:1 v/v to the extraction buffer used) was then added to the mixture and samples were vortexed well and kept on ice for 10 min; (3) after thawing, cellular debris and starch grains were pelleted at 10,000 \times g for 5 min at 5 $^{\circ}$ C; (4) the supernatant was then collected into a new RNase-free tube to which $\frac{1}{2}$ volume of chlo-

roform:isoamyl alcohol (24:1) was added; (5) the mixture was then vortexed well and centrifuged at 10,000 g for 5 min at 5 $^{\circ}$ C (this separation resulted in a clear upper phase, a whitish mid-phase that contains most of the proteins and starch complexes, and a dark lower phase with solid debris); (6) the upper phase was further extracted twice using phenol:chloroform (1:1 v/v); (7) nucleic acids were then precipitated from the upper clear phase by adding 1/10 volume of 3 M sodium acetate and two times the volume of absolute ethanol (tubes were placed

(A) RNA isolated using Qiagen RNEasy Kit (Qiagen Inc., Hilden Germany; Q); TRIzol Reagent (GIBCO, Invitrogen Inc.; T); Stirn et al (1995) RNA isolation method (S) and the new procedure described here using dry rice seeds (lane 1) and germinated rice seeds at 12 h (2), 24 h (3), 48 h (4), and 72 h (5) after the start of imbibition. The samples were separated on 1.5% nondenaturing Tris-boric-EDTA (TBE)-agarose gel and stained with ethidium bromide. Locations of genomic DNA (gDNA) and 25s and 18s rRNA are indicated. **(B)** Amplified products from isolated RNA using the new method, after DNase treatment (Promega) and reverse-transcribed PCR (RT-PCR) using SuperScript One-Step RT-PCR (Invitrogen Inc.) using GAPDH forward primer: 5'-GCAGGAACCCTGAGGAGATC-3' and reverse primer: 5'-TTCCCCCTCCAGTCCTTGCT-3'. A 1-kb DNA ladder (L) is shown to mark the expected fragment size. **(C)** Amplified RT-PCR products from Actin forward primer: 5'-ACGAGCTTCCTGATGGACA-3' and reverse primer: 5'-ATGGGTCAGACTCGTCGTAC-3'. Lane 6 is the control for -RT, indicating no contaminating gDNA after DNase treatment.

in ice to hasten precipitation or optionally put at 5 °C overnight); (8) the pellet was collected by centrifugation at 10,000 \times g for 5 min at 5 °C and resuspended in 50 μ L DEPC-treated water; (9) RNA precipitation was performed using 1/10 volume of 2.5 M lithium chloride plus two volumes of absolute ethanol and samples were placed at -20 °C for 30 min; (10) samples were then centrifuged at 10,000 \times g for 10 min, and the RNA pellet was washed with 70% ethanol, air-dried, dissolved in a final volume of 50 μ L DEPC-treated water, and stored at -20 °C. Following gel visualization and RNA quantitation using a UV spectrophotometer, samples were treated with DNase following suppliers' standard protocols.

The above procedure was found to be effective in obtaining good quantity and quality of total RNA from rice seeds for gene expression studies as shown by

the reverse-transcribed PCR (RT-PCR) products in Figures 1B and 1C. The use of 1% sarcosyl instead of SDS increased NaCl and the addition of β -mercaptoethanol as a protein denaturant and RNase inhibitor, as modifications of Stirn et al (1995) extraction buffer solution, greatly improved quality and yield. Another important step was the use of ice during the lysis step, in contrast to other methods performed at room or higher temperatures. Although heat softens the cell walls, it also breaks most of the polysaccharides and makes the extraction mixture viscous. Double extraction using phenol: chloroform adapted from Stirn's protocol uses an additional step but ensures elimination of other interfering substances such as polysaccharides, polyphenols, and other cellular debris. The average total RNA yield from this procedure is 10 μ g 100 mg⁻¹ seed tissues, which is comparable

with yields obtained using TRIzol reagent on leaves. Positive results were also obtained with rice leaf and root tissues besides dry and germinated rice seeds (data not shown). The new procedure could effectively substitute for commercial RNA isolation kits when using tissues with high carbohydrates such as rice seeds.

References

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